

Supplementary Figure 3

Supplementary Fig. 3. RT-qPCR analysis demonstrated an increased expression of MMP3 (**B**, $p < 0.001$) and MMP9 (**C**, $p < 0.001$), but not MMP2 (**A**) and MMP14 (**D**) mRNA following IL-1 β stimulation in human fetal astrocytes; (**B**) MMP3 expression was decreased in cells transfected with the antagomiR of miR-155 ($p < 0.001$) or mimic of miR-146a ($p < 0.001$) after IL-1 β stimulation; (**A-D**) The expression of MMPs did not change in transfected cells compared to control (lipofectamine vehicle) when IL-1 β was not applied; *** $p < 0.01$, Mann-Whitney U test, error bars depict the standard error of the mean; c – control, anti-155 - antagomiR of miR-155.